

Security Challenges Facing the Internet of Things in Academic Libraries

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ABSTRACT

Internet of Things (IoT) is a term used to conceptualise an idea of a network of connected devices communicating with each other over the internet. While IoT has presented humans with substantial scopes of convenience in the service industry, there lies inherent vulnerabilities and threats in IoT infrastructures that present security challenges. The security challenges of using IoTs in academic libraries are discussed in this paper. The 4-layered IoT architecture is presented, and vulnerabilities in each layer are discussed. The challenges are those that are inherent from sensory devices such as RFID, WSNs, barcodes, and scanners. The security challenges of IoT in academic libraries threaten the expectation of privacy of students, faculty members and university staff. The security challenges also present large financial risks to the institution and its affiliates. Non-technical, socially engineered attacks are also a security challenge to IoTs in academic libraries with grave implications to personal security of its patrons. The implications of IoT vulnerabilities for academic libraries are presented, and recommendations are made to address the security challenges of using IoTs in academic libraries.

Keywords: Internet of Things, Academic Libraries, IoT, Security, Vulnerability, Threat

Words count: 3138 words

1 Introduction

1.1 Internet of Things (IoT) Definition

The “Internet of Things” (IoT) is a term used to conceptualise the idea of devices communicating with each other over the Internet. The term was coined by Kevin Ashton in 1999 [1] and have been attempted to be defined, or described by researchers in the years to follow. However, IoT’s applications are broad in nature, and is relevant in virtually every industry imaginable, for which a specific definition is difficult to propose. From the definitions that have been presented over the years, a broad description of IoT can be presented. IoT is a network of physical objects, where the objects have embedded technologies that allow them to sense the changes in their external surroundings, and the observed changes are wirelessly communicated to the other devices in the network over the internet [2], [3].

IoT has presented humans with substantial scopes of convenience in the service industry. The mesh of interconnected devices communicating, with each other with little to no human intervention, making decisions based on smart algorithms, have resulted in smarter and more intelligent service providing ecosystems. IoT’s contribution has been in the development of smart cities, intelligent healthcare systems, highly accurate data analysis in FinTech industry, and in academia, to name a few [4].

1.2 IoT Architecture

IoT is founded upon several underlying technologies. On the network side, the network architecture of IoTs stem from the very first and basic stage of the internet, the World Wide Web, which was essentially a network of interconnected Hypertext Markup Language (HTML), then evolving further during the rapid growth of the internet when social networking sites and blogs became ubiquitous, to finally, the stage now, known as the Semantic Web, which enable extremely fast machine to machine communication [1]. On the physical side, IoT is heavily reliant on technologies such as Radio Frequency Identification (RFID), and Wireless Sensor Networks (WSN) [5]. The communication between the objects in the physical plane happens through bits of messages traversing through the network plane. Formally, these messages are analogue input signals that are received by the physical objects such as RFIDs and WSNs in the physical plane, which gets converted to digital signals, then to computer readable binary digits, after which the bits are processed, and following a set of protocols, transmitted wirelessly to a destination, where the bits are received, and reconstructed back to the message, based on which an action can be taken.

Information from the physical plane, travels through layers of processing. The layers build up the architecture of the IoT. It is generally accepted that an IoT architecture has 4 layers, but some applications may require as little as 3, while others may require as many as 7 [6]. The diagram in Figure 1 presents a 4-layered IoT architecture.

Figure 1 4-Layered IoT Architecture [7]

The first layer is called the perception layer, sometimes also referred to as the physical layer, or sensor layer. The physical layer consists of the sensors, actuators and devices that can receive analogue input signals in the physical world. The second layer is called the Network layer, also known as the transmission layer. The network layer acts as a bridge that connects the physical world to the network. Communication in the network layer can be either wired, or wireless. The network layer establishes communication between the smart devices in an IoT network and transfers data to and from edge infrastructures. The third layer is called support layer where users are authenticated and transmission and reception protocols are verified. The support layer's primary function is to protect against threats and attacks. The fourth and final layer is called the application layer. Based on the input signals received in the perception layer, the necessary applications from those input devices are carried out in the application layer. For example, when a person approaches the doorway of a smart home, the person's presence is detected in the perception layer, and the homeowner is notified about the event in their smartphone in the application layer.

These four layers make it possible for devices to communicate with each other. Virtually, any device that can be integrated into an IoT architecture can become a part of the IoT network. This allows for versatility and diversity in where IoTs can be applied with substantial managerial implications. For instance, researchers, and practitioners have proposed and realised the application of IoT in academic libraries.

1.3 IoT in Academic Libraries

The proposed and practiced applications of IoT in academic libraries are aimed at providing faster, more accurate, and convenient library services. IoT networks provide low-cost, real-time data about the library premises including current building occupancy, catalogue management, tracking library items, and monitoring indoor climate, and analysing activities during peak library hours [1]. IoTs can enable locating an item anywhere within the library, even outside its shelf, by triangulating its location using multiple IoT devices [8]. IoTs in academic libraries provide students with better able suggested reading materials based on large datasets of previously occurring similar activities of search queries and checkouts [9].

IoT has also made libraries more efficient with reducing time for requesting, queuing, delivering, renewing and returning library items. This has directly reduced the overhead expenses of libraries allowing for investing in further IoT integration such as smart digital shelves, robot arms, cloud services, improved member cards, and smart kiosks for checkouts, returns and fine collections [10].

With such heavy integration of IoT in academic libraries come heavier implications for deep-rooted security challenges. No network is entirely immune from attacks, and the unconstrained growth of IoTs present attackers to locate vulnerabilities to cause large-scale damage to organisations.

1.4 Research Problem

Substantial research attention has been directed at identifying the threats and vulnerabilities that are inherent, and still developing, in IoT systems. One new area of application of IoT is in academic libraries. However, not much research has been focused on identifying how these security threats will affect the people who rely on IoT in academic libraries. Security systems in academic libraries deserve more attention as the integration of technology into library operations management is inevitable. This gap in the research has to be addressed. This study aims to address this gap in the research and thereby make important contribution into the growing body of literature of IoT security systems.

2 Methodology

This study follows a descriptive research methodology using secondary information sources through a literature review of existing published journal articles. The literature search was conducted through search queries in journal databases and academic search engines. The journal databases and academic search engines chosen for this study were Google Scholar, IEEE Xplore, Informit, Internet Archive Scholar, JSTOR: Journal Storage, ResearchGate, ScienceOpen, ScienceDirect, Semantic Scholar, and SpringerLink. For the purpose of this study, articles from 2016 to 2021 were considered for review only. This was ensured by setting the date range of article publication within the specified range.

A list of journal articles was compiled from the initial search results from each of the journal databases and academic search engines. The articles in the list were then screened by title, only considering those that had direct relevance to IT infrastructures. The remaining articles were then further screened by reviewing the abstract and keywords. Only those articles that specified the term, “IoT”, and any of the terms “Security”, “Threats”, “Vulnerabilities”, “Attacks”, “Prevention”, or “Academic library” were considered for reading. The final criterion was to read through the remaining articles in its entirety, and determine its relevance based on the extensiveness and quality of description of the security challenges of IoT systems provided.

3 Discussion

3.1 Fundamental security challenges of IoT in Academic Libraries

IoT systems are vulnerable to threats on each layer of its architecture. Starting with the perception layer, where sensors such as RFIDs, WSNs, barcodes, and scanners exist, attackers can gain access to these physical devices, or even replicate these devices for their personal use and gain. In academic libraries, these sensors exist in library cards, book tags, shelves, kiosks, counters, and doorways. The vulnerabilities of physical devices in the perception layer present the following security challenges to students, staff, and faculty members:

1. Eavesdropping: Attackers get access to the messages being transmitted over the physical devices, allowing them to steal sensitive information being transmitted over a network [11].
2. Node capture: An attacker takes control of a gateway node, getting access to all information that is passed through the node. The attacker can also replicate the node and spread further attacks in the network [12].
3. Fake node: Fake data is introduced into the system through a fake node that is created by the attacker which disrupts the flow of actual information. Large scale attacks of fake nodes can disrupt the entire network [12].
4. Jamming attack: These attacks are usually carried out using radio signals. The radio signals can scramble input signals at perception layer [13].
5. Resource depletion attack: This type of attack forces a node to constantly retransmit and receive the data endlessly till all its resources are completely depleted [14].
6. Relay attack: The attacker introduces a relay node thereby gaining access to all the information that is passed through the relay node [13].
7. Play back attack: When an attacker listens in or eavesdrops on a conversation, they are able to pick up information that are validated by the receiver on the other end [15]. The attacker can then play back the same information, which the receiver on the other end can perceive as being a valid request providing the attacker with additional information.

If the attacker gains access to the network layer of an IoT system, they can exploit security issues that are related to authentication mechanism of network layers. Network layers are very prone to being attacked because of how commonly attackers have been able to exploit an IoT system based on the following security threats.

8. Denial of Service (DoS) attack: Actual users registered in the database and authorised to access other devices and nodes in the network get denied their authority. Attackers usually overwhelm the IoT system with redundant and repeated requests which takes up all the resources and authentic users are therefore denied the service they are seeking [16]. A DoS attack in an academic library setting can bring library operations to a halt, causing disruption in learning, management, and operations.
9. Man in the Middle (MiTM) attack: The attacker finds a way to receive a message, is able to alter the contents of the message, and send it forward to the actual receiver. This can go undetected and both the transmitter and receiver can mistakenly communicate wrong information back and forth. Furthermore, actions based on requests by either sender or receiver can be manipulated by the attacker [7]. Through MiTM attack, personal information of students, staff and faculty members can be exposed to an attacker.
10. Storage attack: This is an attack on the database where user information is stored. In addition to getting access to personal information, attackers can exploit this further by replicating the information, use the information to obtain access through restricted gateways to launch further attacks or gain access to information with higher clearance levels [17]. Storage attacks in academic libraries can potentially erase, corrupt, or destroy entire databases, incurring huge financial losses for the institution.
11. Exploit attack: Attacks that take advantage of an existing vulnerability typical of an application or software, are categorised as exploit attacks, usually carried out with the intention to gain access to and steal information stored in a database [18]. Personal information of students, staff and faculty members can be accessed by attackers using exploit attacks.

The support layer attempts to provide security to the IoT's architecture where information goes through confirmation and authentication to protect the users against possible attacks. Usually, the support layer provides this protection through the use of passwords, pins, keys, or answers to questions known only to users. Attackers can still find ways to exploit vulnerabilities in the support layer.

12. DoS Attack: When DoS attacks are successfully performed on the network layer, the support layer reacts by continuing to authenticate and verify the requests continually till system resources get focused on the point of attack denying services to actual users in the system.

13. Malicious insider attack: This type of attack involves an unethical and immoral act by someone who has access on an administrative level. User with the authorisation to access information of others can exploit their position in the IoT network's administrative process. The prevention of such attacks can go undetected as authorised activities would not be flagged as inappropriate by a software [19]. This presents concerns of privacy, and personal safety for students, staff and faculty members, as the attacker can access many of their personal information.

Finally, in the application layer, where processes communicate with each other through ports, the following security vulnerabilities present challenges.

14. DoS attack: Successful DoS attack can traverse all the way from the network layer to the application layer. The excessive usage of resources can cause the application to crash in this layer.

15. Phishing attack: This sort of attack happens in the physical world, where a user with malicious intent impersonates a known associate of another user to get information. There are no limits to the amount of personal information that can be received through phishing attacks. Information that are not stored in the database but are personal to a user can be extracted through careful, socially engineered phishing attacks [20]. Phishing attacks in academic libraries present significant risk to the personal safety of students, staff and faculty members.

16. Malicious code injection: These are codes that are entered into a part of the software which causes the software to behave in unexpected ways, often resulting in damage to the system. These sorts of attacks can go undetected and bypass anti-virus software [21]. Malicious code injection poses significant risk to the academic institution's reputation, financial security, and stakeholders' interests.

17. Session hijacking attack: A user's existing web session can get hijacked by an attacker and cause the user to lose access [22].

18. Cross site scripting: Like malicious code injection, cross site scripting is also an injection attack. The attacker finds a vulnerability in the system, injects their own code, and clients on the other end receive an altered version of the software they are expected to interact with, from where the attacker can gain authenticated information from the user [23].

IoT systems nowadays are increasing in size, and the amount of data that flows through the different layers in the architecture, and the nodes of the network, have the characteristic of being fast, real-time, and large. Security challenges associated with the growth of large networks with uncountable nodes are discussed in the next section.

The security challenges discussed in the corresponding journal article, and the nature of the security challenges is presented in Table 1.

Table 1 Summary of security challenges appearing in publications

Architecture Layer	Security Challenge	Discussed in
Perception Layer	Eavesdropping attacks	[11]
	Clone Node attacks	[12]
	Fake Node attacks	
	Jamming attacks	[13]
	Relay attacks	
Network Layer	Man in the Middle (MiTM) attack	[7]
	Denial of Service attack (DoS) attack	[16]
	Storage attack	[17]
	Exploit attack	[18]
Support layer	Denial of Service attack (DoS) attack	[16]
	Malicious insider attack	[19]
Application Layer	Denial of Service attack (DoS) attack	[16]
	Phishing Attack	[20]
	Malicious code injection	[21]
	Session Hijacking attack	[22]
	Cross Site Scripting	[23]

3.2 Security challenges in large IoT networks

As the network size and infrastructure grows, characteristic vulnerabilities of IoT networks become more difficult to manage and defend. Attackers come with malicious intentions of ransoming money, causing personal harm, damaging organisation reputation, cyber-terrorism, notoriety, and harassment, to name a few. As the size of a network grows, monitoring the network demands higher computation and processing power for robust security [7], [24], [25]. The security protocols of small scale networks, usually those that existed prior to the system being upgraded to integrate IoT devices, are not scalable up to accommodate the ever increasing number of nodes and connected devices [4]. In academic libraries, end-users, such as students and faculty members are also unaware of potential threats and risks or points of entry that attackers exploit, meaning, any exploitable invalid action by an end-user presents

security risks. Lack of user-knowledge was one of the weak points exploited during cyber-attacks like Mirai [26].

The current body of research is focused on identifying those vulnerabilities that come with the large-scale nature of today's IoT systems. The amount of data processed per time period, and the analysis of the data, often times require machine learning, deep learning, and reinforcement learning algorithms, which means new security challenges are being presented as research continues. The perception layer in IoT in academic libraries is a source of big and fast-moving data that can create large, unstructured, datasets. It is important to consider the security issues that are raised when such large networks are producing such huge amount of data. [27] surveyed various frameworks proposed for protecting IoT networks, each with a unique solution. However, the lack of consensus in security protocols indicate that there is no standardisation that is being followed, meaning attackers will have multiple alternative methods of attack, each of which have to be individually defended against. [21] reviewed various malware attacks in IoT systems that threaten the privacy of users, their messages, and their devices. These malware attacks become increasingly dangerous as the system becomes more decentralised, for example, in fog computing systems as there are no protocols to protect the large amount of data that is constantly being transferred. [28] further commented on vulnerabilities regarding datasets, identifying that there is a lack of IoT dataset that can allow evaluating deep networks for network security analysis.

[29] brought to attention the necessity of real-time data for real-time threat detection through robust algorithms. The existing algorithms are not exhaustive and efficient enough to ensure complete protection from Denial-of-Service (DoS) or distributed DoS (DDoS) attacks in large IoT networks. The datasets themselves tend to be unstructured and unbalanced, and according to [30], there is a significant lack of deep learning models that are capable of processing large, unbalanced and unstructured datasets. The challenge of identifying a vulnerability itself is amplified in large networks such as IoTs. [25] explored the various IoT vulnerabilities and how they are assessed, and found there have not been exhaustive research conducted in presenting intelligent vulnerability assessment techniques. Finally, [31] conducted a systematic survey of recently proposed solutions based on deep-learning and machine learning algorithms aimed at securing IoT networks. Their findings suggest that vulnerabilities are constantly being presented as the concept of IoT networks continue to evolve, and that most solutions have not taken into consideration the growth of number of vulnerabilities. Academic institutions therefore have particular responsibility to all its patrons, including the library staff and

administrators before investing in IoT in their libraries, as unconstrained growth in their IoT network can result in large-scale damages. Implications of IoT vulnerabilities for academic libraries, and future recommendations are presented next in the conclusion section.

Table 2 summarises the major security challenges of large IoT networks.

Table 2 Major security challenges of large IoT networks

Challenge	Authors
High computation and processing requirement for improving security	[4], [7], [24], [25]
Increased vulnerability due to decentralisation of large networks	[21]
Lack of research focusing on large networks	[25]
Not all end users are knowledgeable enough to ensure safe operations abiding protocols	[26]
Lack of consensus in security protocol and standardisation	[27]
Large networks are not supported by equally large datasets for analysing vulnerabilities	[28]
Lack of real-time threat detection due to lack of real-time data	[29]
Lack of deep learning models or sophisticated algorithm capable of handling large networks	[30]
Constantly evolving models of large network structures continue to present new vulnerabilities	[31]

4 Conclusion

4.1 Implications of IoT vulnerabilities for Academic Libraries

IoT systems have vulnerabilities that threaten the personal safety and reasonable expectation of privacy and security of users. The integration of IoT in academic libraries has undoubtedly presented a convenient, efficient, and effective service to its patrons. However, students, faculty members, administrations, and the institution itself, risk being victims of cyber-attacks that can significantly affect their financial security, reputation, and career.

IoTs are being adopted widely and it has become an urgent necessity to have standardised security measures that is robust, up-to-date and includes the latest in artificial intelligence, machine learning, deep learning, and reinforcement learning algorithms. Particularly, the rate at which IoT networks are growing, it is not feasible to scale up existing solutions to provide protection, especially to students and faculty members, who have the expectation of reasonable security when accessing academic libraries.

4.2 Recommendations

It is being suggested that more research should be focused on addressing the gap in protocols and standardisation made specifically for IoT networks. This should be the first step going ahead, after which further specialisation can present frameworks based on standardised practices to be tailored to academic libraries.

It is further being suggested that more resource should be allocated in analysing the unstructured datasets that are created during the operations of IoT in academic libraries to identify outliers and edge cases that could potentially indicate malicious activity. This can present the opportunity for creating training examples of actual malicious activity against general outlier cases. Further models can then be trained based on the predictive capacity of existing models.

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